

1 Parameters

Table 1: Major Physical and Economic Parameters of the HIMs

Parameter	Value
\bar{p}_m^{ELE}	500 kW
$\underline{p}_m^{\text{ELE}}$	65 kW
\bar{p}^{ASU}	500 kW
η^{ASU}	11.9
M^{HST}	60 kg
C^{BESS}	250, 500 kWh
$\bar{p}^{\text{BESS}}, \underline{p}^{\text{BESS}}$	50, 70 kW
$\overline{\text{SOC}}^{\text{BESS}}$	0.95
$\underline{\text{SOC}}^{\text{BESS}}$	0.1
$\overline{\text{SOE}}^{\text{HST}}$	0.9
$\underline{\text{SOE}}^{\text{HST}}$	0.2
λ^{NH_3}	5 CNY/kg
Faraday constant F	96485 C/mol
$V_{\text{REF}}^{\text{ELE}}$	2 V
η^{ELE}	0.95

Table 2: DC-MATRPO Algorithm Parameters

Hyper Parameter	Value
KL threshold	0.01
Actor/critic learning rate	5e-5
Discount factor	0.99
Optimizer	Adam
MLP Layer	1
Hidden sizes	256
Line search fraction	0.5